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INDICATORS OF RESEARCH INTEGRITY

An initial exploration of the landscape, opportunities and challenges

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Prepared on behalf of UK Research and Innovation, Cancer Research UK and GuildHE
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BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE

Informing future discussion on research integrity indicators

UKRI, Cancer Research UK and GuildHE commissioned Research Consulting to investigate potential indicators of research integrity. This work sought to explore indicators that could help research organisations, funders of research and research infrastructures, researchers, publishers and others to identify and promote high levels of research integrity, building on the principles and commitments in the UK Concordat to Support Research Integrity. This Executive Summary provides an overview of Research Consulting's findings. It is intended to inform further discussions across the research system

and recognise the potential challenges, benefits and risks in adopting indicators in the area of research integrity, with the ultimate aim of improving partnership, collaboration and ways to achieve higher levels of research integrity.

This research was informed by:

- a desk review of over 120 sources, including academic articles, reports, disciplinary guidelines, concordats, tools, generalist articles and relevant websites; and
- a set of 22 stakeholder interviews with individuals from the UK, Europe and North America.

Definitions

In the context of this work, we considered an “indicator” as a quantitative or qualitative factor or variable that provides a reliable means to measure achievement, to reflect the changes connected to an intervention, or to help assess the performance or state of play of an actor or system.

As research can fall short in terms of its integrity for a number of reasons, many of which do not reflect the intent of researchers, a wide range of behaviours are relevant to this discussion, including

honest errors, poor research practices, questionable research practices and research misconduct.

Measuring levels of research integrity arising from the above behaviours is difficult and likely to require a mix of lagging indicators, which can help measure progress or performance against a baseline, and leading indicators, which can help measure practices and behaviours that are, in theory, expected to lead to change or performance in the future.

POTENTIAL PURPOSES FOR INTEGRITY INDICATORS

Although many stakeholders have an interest in research integrity, research performing organisations, individual researchers, research funders and publishers are described in the literature as the key actors. The following are seen as their main roles and responsibilities:

- Research performing organisations: Cultivating and fostering a culture of research integrity; Ensuring that institutional behaviours are in line with external expectations of integrity; Conducting investigations in cases where research integrity is questioned.
- Individual researchers: Aligning with disciplinary standards and expectations from their organisations, research funders and publishers.
- Research funders: Setting expectations of research integrity via their evaluation, review and award criteria; Monitoring funded grants.
- Publishers: Setting expectations of submitting authors; Supporting the investigation of cases of misconduct.

To support the sector in meeting its research integrity ambitions, the present study has hypothesised the following potential purposes for research integrity indicators:

Constituency	Potential purposes
<p>Funders, research performing organisations, publishers and sector bodies (including Concordat signatories, the UK Research Integrity Office, the UK Reproducibility Network and learned societies)</p>	<p>1. Understanding, planning and evaluating interventions that aim to improve the research environment, the integrity and therefore the overall quality of research 2. Assessing whether research(er) practices and behaviours are in line with organisational expectations around research integrity (e.g. Concordat requirements, grant terms and conditions, author guidelines)</p>
<p>UK Committee on Research Integrity (on behalf of the research community)</p>	<p>As above, plus: 3. Identifying systemic pressures affecting research integrity and harnessing opportunities for change among funders, research performing organisations, publishers and sector bodies to support an environment in which researchers can work with high levels of research integrity</p>
<p>Meta-researchers (i.e. those carrying out research on research itself)</p>	<p>4. Enabling (meta)researchers to reference an agreed framework for evidence in planning and reporting their research into aspects of the research system related to research integrity</p>

PRIORITISING AREAS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDICATORS

Building on the Concordat, we have identified a range of indicative 'facets' of research integrity arising from the five principles, considering these as distinct areas of research integrity where the creation of indicators may be considered.

Based on our research and consultation, we built a three-dimensional pilot framework to identify facets where early progress appears achievable with regard to the creation of research integrity indicators. This is covered in more detail in our [discussion document](#), but the mind map on the following page provides an overview of our analysis.

Our qualitative assessment of feasibility may be used as a proxy to decide where to start creating research integrity indicators, meaning that high-feasibility ones are more likely to be suitable for immediate progress. However, areas marked as low or medium feasibility should also be carefully considered in the short term, to ensure that the right discussions and efforts take place to underpin future work.

The prioritisation of facets is preliminary at this stage and has been developed by Research Consulting based on the evidence gathered and analysed.

Potential approaches to create indicators

An indicators framework will need to achieve a balance between the benefits of using metrics and the bureaucracy required to create them.

We have identified the following potential approaches to create indicators:

- **Survey instruments:** Online surveys that may include a combination of closed-ended questions and narrative statements.
- **Reporting based on organisational management systems:** Export and aggregation of data from organisational management systems.

- **Simple database queries:** Queries of existing databases, typically via APIs, seeking to answer quantitative questions.
- **Text and data mining / machine learning:** Programmatic analysis of databases, qualitative or quantitative data, based on sophisticated methods and significant tailoring around a question.

We report scepticism about the use of wholly quantitative indicators, as well as concerns about the risk of ranking and gaming.

FACETS OF RESEARCH INTEGRITY

CURRENT TRENDS AND STAKEHOLDER VIEWS

Currently, indicators are mainly conceptualised around publishing practices and research misconduct, focusing for example on numbers and reasons for article retractions, shares of open access publications, prevalence of data sharing and use of reporting guidelines. The Hong Kong Principles for assessing researchers offer some additional examples of indicators around the research process and focus more broadly on research cultures, such as the use of altmetrics and markers of impact and engagement.

"In some cases, the indicator becomes the driver of the whole sector. If we start getting league tables, and everyone knows that their institutional reputation will depend on where they end up based on the indicators, these will become an extremely perverse incentive."

Quick wins in the development of indicators are likely to centre on publishing and dissemination activities, including with regard to articles, preprints, research data, methods, protocols and more. However, this risks failing to heed the warning that "not everything that can be counted counts, and not everything that counts can be counted." Indicators centred on publishing and dissemination also suffer from potential concerns around (i) data quality

and comprehensiveness; and (ii) the extent to which the above-mentioned practices apply to different disciplines.

Furthermore, we note that we haven't considered research cultures, equality, diversity and inclusion and bullying and harassment as part of our core scope of work. It may therefore be appropriate to include these topics in a future indicators framework or to examine them as part of dedicated exercises, as they were mentioned by several contributors alongside the idea of research culture.

Overall, the use of indicators will need to overcome fears of benchmarking or ranking of organisations and individuals, and we note that the development of wholly quantitative measures was strongly opposed. This partly arises from concerns of potential issues such as miscalculation, misalignment and perverse incentives, and the risk that indicators at one level of the system may lead to unintended consequences for stakeholders at other levels of the system.

"The risk of setting up an intervention is that we replace one set of incentives that are creating perverse outcomes with another set of incentives creating different perverse outcomes. It's a whole system, and any improvements will be a really long game."

CONCLUSIONS AND PRINCIPLES FOR FUTURE WORK

Our research and consultation indicated that there is currently limited or no use of research integrity indicators, at least not beyond the walls of individual organisations. Where organisational metrics exist, these tend to focus on specific internal matters and are not shareable nor comprehensive in most cases, even if the overarching themes and aims are similar across organisations. Any attempt to develop indicators will have to be guided by the shifting nature of what the sector means by “research integrity” and the growing range of stakeholders that have to be engaged.

We identified a set of three principles that should underpin future work on research integrity indicators, with the expectation that disciplinary and organisational differences and requirements will be weighed up throughout. We recommend that these principles are carefully considered in any future work in this area to lay the foundation for sustainable and credible indicators of research integrity.

<p>Refine the goals of indicators</p> <p>Continue the discussion and further refine the possible purposes of indicators.</p>	<p>Kick off a broader discussion</p> <p>Do not focus on wholly quantitative indicators and engage the research community.</p>	<p>Foster integrity and avoid rankings</p> <p>Ensure that indicators are used to foster and promote good practices rather than for raking organisations.</p>
<p>Remain aware of challenges</p> <p>Remember that miscalculation, gaming and misalignment should be considered.</p>	<p>Examine a range of approaches</p> <p>Build on the range of approaches we have highlighted and minimise burdens.</p>	<p>Pursue co-creation in any next steps</p> <p>Arbitrarily set indicators will be opposed: focus on co-creation to make progress.</p>
<p>Consider equality, diversity and inclusion</p> <p>Indicators will apply to a wide range of contexts: consider equality, diversity and inclusion.</p>	<p>Legend</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Foster and share good research integrity practice 2. Consider a breadth of approaches 3. Ensure co-creation and inclusion	

THANK YOU FOR READING

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Cancer Research UK is the largest charitable funder of cancer research in the world, funding around 50% of all publicly funded cancer research here in the UK. We want to accelerate progress and see 3 in 4 people surviving their cancer by 2034. Cancer Research UK supports research into the prevention, detection and treatment of cancer through the work of over 4,000 scientists, doctors and nurses. Our research strategy is underpinned by our principles: to invest in creative people who can deliver research of the highest quality, to support research to reduce cancer inequalities and improve outcomes for everyone, and to involve people affected by cancer in our work.

GuildHE is an officially recognised representative body for UK higher education. Our members include universities, university colleges, further education colleges and specialist institutions from both the traditional and private (“not for profit” and “for profit”) sectors. Through our dedicated research consortium, GuildHE Research, we engage the full diversity of our institutions, people, and places in research and innovation, and advocate for the recognition and support of excellent research wherever it is found. We help our members to embed a positive and constructive research culture, develop robust research and innovation strategies, and establish appropriate infrastructure through which they can drive forward their ambitions.

UK Research and Innovation works in partnership with universities, research organisations, businesses, charities, and government to create the best possible environment for research and innovation to flourish. As the UK’s largest public funder of research and innovation it is our responsibility to ensure the health of the system as a whole, now and in the future. As a steward of this system, we work together with our many partners to benefit everyone through knowledge, talent and ideas. Operating across the whole of the UK with a combined budget of more than £7 billion, UK Research and Innovation brings together the seven research councils, Innovate UK and Research England.

Research Consulting is a mission-driven research and scholarly communication consultancy, working with national and international organisations to help them make the most of their research processes and findings. We are active participants in the research ecosystem, and our work covers all aspects of the research life-cycle – including policy, funding, management, publishing and knowledge exchange. Any questions? Get in touch via: andrea.chiarelli@research-consulting.com.